

Green chemistry approach : Synthesis of silver nanoparticles by using lime juice (*Citrus aurantifolia*) extract and their evaluation as antibacterial agent

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Abstract : Nanoparticles of silver have been synthesized by the reaction of silver nitrate, lime juice (*Citrus aurantifolia*) and sodium bicarbonate by adopting green chemistry approach and characterized by FT-IR , UV-Visible spectral analysis, P-XRD, Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and elemental analysis by EDAX technique which revealed that silver nanoparticles were in metallic form. The average particle size was found 32 nm. They were screened for antibacterial activities on two gram +ve bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and two gram -ve bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* by adopting disc diffusion method *in vitro*. The results of antibacterial studies suggested that Ag nanoparticles can be used as effective growth inhibitors in microorganisms, making them applicable to medical devices and antimicrobial control systems.

Keywords : Nanoparticles, P-XRD, antibacterial, Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

Introduction

In the recent years, the metallic nanoparticles have been reported to exhibit remarkable antibacterial properties due to their large surface area to volume ratio, which is of interest to researchers due to the increasing microbial resistance against metal ions, antibiotics and the development of resistant strains^{1,2}. New applications of nanoparticles and nanomaterials are emerging rapidly^{3,4}. The huge interest in metal nanoparticles is due to their unexpected physical and chemical properties shown at nanoscale. Noble metal nanoparticles have generated a great interest as colourants^{5,6}, metal coating^{7,8}, electronics⁹⁻¹¹, optics¹² and chemical catalysis^{13,14}.

A number of approaches are available for the synthesis of metal nanoparticles for example, chemical reduction¹⁵, electrochemical techniques¹⁶, photochemical reactions in reverse micelles¹⁷ and now a days *via* green chemistry route¹⁸. The use of environmentally benign material like plants leaf extract¹⁹, bacteria²⁰, fungi²¹ and enzymes²² in synthesis of nanoparticles offers numerous benefits of eco-friendliness and compatibility for pharmaceutical and other biomedical applications as they do not use toxic chemicals for the synthesis protocol. Green syn-

thesis provides advancement over chemical and physical method as it is cost effective, environment friendly, easily scaled up for large scale synthesis and in this method there is no need to use high pressure, energy, temperature and toxic chemicals.

In this research paper the silver nanoparticles have been synthesized by adopting green chemistry approach and characterized by FT-IR, P-XRD, transmission electron microscope (TEM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM) with EDAX detector. The antibacterial significance of these nanoparticles has been screened on human pathogenic microorganisms *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* (gram +ve) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve). The zone of inhibition and MIC value were measured after 24 h of incubation at 37 °C.

Results and discussion

FT-IR measurements were carried out with model Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer RxI operated in the range of 4000–500 cm⁻¹ in KBr. UV-Visible spectral analysis were carried on Lab-India UV-Visible spectrophotometer UV 3000⁺. P-XRD measurement were carried out on

XPRT-PRO X-ray diffractometer (PAN analytical Bv, the Netherland), operated at a voltage of 45 kV and a current of 40 mA with Cu K_{α} radiation in a θ - 2θ configuration. The transmission electron microscope (TEM) measurements were carried out by using model Morgani (FEI) Netherland 268 D, operated on accelerating voltage of 60–80 kV with two different resolutions 100 nm and 200 nm. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersing analysis of X-ray (EDAX) measurements were carried out by using with model JEOL Model JSM-6390LV and EDS Model JEOL Model JED-2300, at resolution of 3 nm to 8 nm and magnification 5 X to 300,000 X (Both in High and Low Vacuum Modes), operating on voltage of 1 pA to 1 mA.

FT-IR spectral studies :

In the FT-IR spectra (Fig.1) of the silver nanoparticles the absorption bands at 3429, 1680, 1392, 1277 and 836 cm^{-1} have been obtained which may be attributed due to

O–H stretching vibrations, C=O stretching vibrations, C–H bending vibrations, C–O–C stretching vibrations and C–H deformation vibrations out of planes respectively. These bands may be attributed due to citric acid, formed as a by product during the reduction of Ag^{+} to metallic Ag, which may be present in the sample as impurities. Furthermore, no band below 600 cm^{-1} (metal-ligand sensitive region) has obtained in the FT-IR spectra which suggested that nanoparticles of silver have formed in the form of metallic silver.

UV-Visible spectral analysis :

In the UV-Visible spectra (Fig. 2) of the silver nanoparticles a strong broad peak at 432 nm was observed. Observation of this strong peak is clearly indicating²³ the formation of Me-NPs. The broad peak indicating the polydispersed²⁴ nature of the synthesized Ag-NPs.

Powder XRD studies :

The composition of nanoparticles was determined by the powder X-ray diffractometer technique. The diffrac-

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of silver nanoparticles.

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectrum of silver nanoparticles.

tion graph (Fig. 3) was recorded in the range of $2^\circ < 2\theta < 70^\circ$. The P-XRD spectra displayed that the silver nanoparticles were crystalline in nature. Full width at half maximum was used to find size distribution of the particles. Theoretical model suggests that with the increase of the particles size the full width at half maximum is also increased. The crystallite domain size was calculated from the width of the P-XRD peaks, assuming that they are free from non-uniform strains, using the Debye-Scherrer formula.

$$D = \frac{0.94\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

D is the average crystallite domain size perpendicular to the reflecting planes, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and θ is the diffraction angle. To eliminate additional instrumental broadening the FWHM was corrected using the FWHM from a large grains Si sample.

$$\beta_{\text{Corrected}} = (\text{FWHM}_{\text{sample}}^2 - \text{FWHM}_{\text{Si}}^2)^{1/2}$$

This modified formula²⁵ is applicable only when the crystallite size is smaller than 100 nm. Different 2θ values 19.2877, 21.7225, 27.7841, 31.5025, 32.4722, 33.2579, 35.5579, 36.2711, 39.0012, 43.1438, 61.9752 and 63.4575 of P-XRD graph correspond to the particle size (calculated by the Scherrer equation) 55.4, 28.2, 48.9, 27.6, 17.1, 30.7, 29.5, 34.4, 33.0, 15.3, 29.8 and 34.2 nm respectively. Among these peaks, the peak at 27.7841, 35.5579, 39.0012, 43.1438, 61.9752 and 63.4575 corre-

spond to the (311), (004), (111), (200), (110) and (112) sets of lattice planes respectively. These planes may be indexed for mixed phase²⁶⁻³⁰ (cubic and hexagonal) of silver nanoparticles. A few unassigned peaks were also noticed in the vicinity of the characteristic peaks. These peaks might be resulted due to the capping agent or stabilizing agent. The average particles size of silver nanoparticles was found 32 nm.

Transmission electron microscopic studies :

TEM images indicated that the size of the silver nanoparticles lies in the range 5 to 60 nm. The average size of the silver nanoparticles was 32 nm. TEM images also indicated that the particles were well dispersed, hexagonal and cubic irregular in shape. However, the shape of particles may be made more clear by the SEM images. The TEM images and particle size distribution graph of the silver nanoparticles have been shown in Fig. 4(A-E).

Scanning electron microscopic studies :

The synthesized nanoparticles were also examined by the SEM for the surface morphology, identification of dopants and their structure determination. The SEM images (Fig. 5(A-C)) of silver nanoparticles exhibited that the silver nanoparticles were hexagonal, cubic irregular and plate shape. The EDAX profile (Fig. 5D) of the silver nanoparticles indicated that the sample contains silver in maximum concentration whereas carbon and oxygen in minimum concentrations. The carbon and oxygen may be present due to citric acid as impurities.

Fig. 3. P-XRD graph of silver nanoparticles.

Fig. 4. (A-D) : TEM images of silver nanoparticles, (E) : particle size distribution graph.

Fig. 5. (A-C) : SEM images of silver nanoparticles, (D) : EDAX profile of silver nanoparticles.

Results of antibacterial activity :

The obtained results of zone of inhibition and photographs of antibacterial study for the silver nanoparticles and standard Gentamicin have been shown in the Table 1 and Figs. 6(a), 6(b), 7(a) and 7(b) respectively. The maxi-

imum zone of inhibitions (Table 1) for *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* were found at 13.8 mm, 12.9 mm, 11.1 mm and 12.0 mm respectively at the lowest concentration of $6.25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ while the zone of inhibitions of

Table 1. Zone of inhibition (in mm) of synthesized silver nanoparticles and standard at different concentrations

Sr. no.	Test concentration ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (SNP/Std.)	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (SNP/Std.)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (SNP/Std.)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (SNP/Std.)
1.	100	19.7/21.9	20.9/21.5	19.1/24.0	20.2/23.7
2.	50	18.1/20.4	19.6/20.0	17.4/22.5	17.9/21.9
3.	25	16.8/18.8	17.8/18.2	14.7/19.1	15.5/19.5
4.	12.5	15.1/17.7	15.3/16.7	13.7/18.7	14.3/17.3
5.	6.25	13.8/15.3	12.9/14.6	11.1/16.2	12.0/15.8

SNP = Silver nanoparticles, Std. = Standard antibiotic (Gentamicin).

Fig. 6(a). Antibacterial trends of silver nanoparticles.

Fig. 6(b). Antibacterial trends of Gentamicin.

standard drug i.e. Gentamicin were found 15.3 mm for *Staphylococcus aureus*, 14.6 mm for *Bacillus subtilis*, 16.2 for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 15.8 for *Escherichia coli* at $6.25 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration.

Materials and method :

Silver nitrate was purchased from Sisco. The Mueller Hinton Agar Media (MHA) for the antibacterial activity was purchased from Hi Media Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. Four

Fig. 7(a). Digital photographs of silver nanoparticles against microorganisms.

Fig. 7(b). Digital photographs of Gentamicin against microorganisms.

bacterial species *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* were obtained from IMTECH Chandigarh, India.

Synthesis of lime juice (Citrus aurantifolia) extract : *Citrus aurantifolia* fruits collected from the local market were peeled and sliced into small pieces and blended with 100 ml deionised water. The blended pulp was then filtered by using muslin cloth to remove solid particles. The liquid was further filtered using Whatman filter paper 1. The filtrate was used for the preparation of nanoparticles.

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles : In a 250 ml beaker 50 ml filtered lime juice was taken. To this, 3.78 g of NaHCO₃ was added very slowly during stirring. 10 ml from this pipette out and diluted up to 50 ml in a volumetric flask. In another beaker, 100 ml of 0.001 M aqueous solution of silver nitrate (16.98 g) was taken and heated up to boiling. To this solution, 10 ml solution from volumetric flask was added drop by drop. During the process solution was mixed vigorously. Solution was heated until color was changed to pale yellow. Then it was removed from the heating element and stirred until cooled at room temperature. The product so obtained was filtered and washed with deionised water. Finally, it was dried in a vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Antibacterial studies :

Disc diffusion method³¹ was used to study the antimicrobial activity of the silver nanoparticles against two gram +ve bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and two gram -ve bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* microorganisms by measuring the zone of inhibition. In this method, discs of 6 mm were loaded with the different concentrations 100, 50, 25, 12.5, 6.25 µg/ml of silver nanoparticles. The bacteria were subcultured in Mueller-Hinton Agar medium. These discs were placed on the solidified culture plates of different microorganism against which the sensitivity has to be measured. These plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. After 24 h the zones of inhibition were measured. The zones of inhibition were measured in mm. Gentamicin was used as a standard drug for antibacterial screening. The mean of maximum zone of inhibition values (in diameter) have been given in Table 1.

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